

Anjeela Pradhan Gorkhaly¹ and Prabha Gautam^{2*}
Tribhuvan University¹; Kathmandu Bernhardt College²
prabha1130@gmail.com*

The Effect of Interest Rate and Inflation on National Savings in Nepal

Abstract: A nation's past, present, and future are all economically connected and this depends in large part on its saving rate. National economy is largely depended on the capital mobilization from the public and to the public. The appropriate disbursement of interest rates on savings and advances can be the key associated factor. These associated factors determine whether the economy experiences inflation or deflation on a macroeconomic scale within the nation. The objective of this study is to examine the trend of Lending Interest Rate, Consumer Price Index, Per Capita Income, GDP, and Gross Domestic Savings and to analyze the relationship of the Lending Interest Rate, Consumer Price Index, Per Capita Income, and GDP with the Gross Domestic Savings of Nepal for the period 2000/01 to 2019/20 by employing a multiple regression model with logarithmic transformation. Required data are collected from secondary sources like Nepal Rastra Bank, World Bank and Ministry of Finance etc. The result of this study indicates a negative but significant relationship between Consumer Price Index and Gross Domestic Savings of Nepal. Likewise, there is a positive but insignificant relation between Lending Interest Rate and GDS of Nepal. Regression result also shows that Per Capita Income is negatively and Gross Domestic Product is positively related with GDS of Nepal.

Keywords: Gross Domestic Savings, Lending Interest Rate, Inflation, per capita Income, economy

Introduction

Economic development refers to the development of capacities that expand the economic capabilities of individuals, firms, industries, and nations. According to Sen (1999), economic development is the sustainable increase in the per capita income of a nation as well as an increase in quality of life and social and environmental development. Various economic and non-economic factors determine the economic development of any nation; economic factors include human resources, capital, technology, and natural resources, whereas non-economic factors include the social and political aspects of a country. All these factors either the economic or non-economic plays a vital role for the growth of country's economy. It is presumed that growth in an economy can foster the living standard of every citizen. This further generates the high purchasing power, high growth on investment thus resources are mobilized to the optimum level which leads to the better return for the economy. Moreover, the economy cycle is generated and can maintain

its peak level for a greater extent. However, not all economy is expected to maintain its consistency in their economy.

A fluctuation in the nation's economy can come from various internal as well as external sources, thus making an impact on its economy by bringing about inflation or deflation in the interest rate, therefore these consequences can lead to a situation where a general public may suffer and the crisis in economy is generated that stops the economy cycle. Rajbhandari (2020) states external forces can create a situation of Crisis Ignorance (CI) and Crisis Avoidance (CA). This generates a larger portion of saving with little or no interest on savings. Crisis Management (CM) in this situation would be to optimally utilizing the resources to fulfil the adequacy level of needs thus inflation can be contained. Inflation and interest rate are considered among the highly pronounced macroeconomic factors in every economy, whether it is developed or underdeveloped. Inflation and interest rate are important variables that make a huge impact on the other macroeconomic factors of the economy.

Saving and investments of a nation are also affected by the interest rate and prevailing inflation of the nation. Saving is the prerequisite for every economy to move forward from the lower level of saving and low growth equilibrium of a nation. A country's saving rate is a key factor in determining how its history, present, and future are all economically related. The economy will experience a vicious spiral of reduced investment, slower growth rate, lower productivity, and lower per capita income if a low level of saving is sustained for an extended period of time. Saving, therefore has a crucial role in economic progress (Ahmed & Asghar, 2010).

Saving is considered as one of the important part of national income, saving is an excess amount of current expenditure and kept in reserve for future use. Simply we can understand savings are usually held in the form of cash or bank deposits. But in a more general sense, saving encompasses the value of all possessions, including financial assets, stocks or inventories, machinery, and real estate (Rehman, Faridi & Bashir, 2010). It is believed that saving plays a collective and essential role for the sustainable future and the economical upliftment of a nation (Nga, 2007). Due to savings, a person and a nation can be financially secure from future uncertainties and contingencies. Savings play a role in safeguarding a nation from economic tremors and bankruptcy (Mboweni, 2008). In addition to promoting economic growth, greater saving rates also give residents more employment options and aid in luring in foreign investors for capital investments (Mboweni, 2008).

According to Khan (1993), any country must increase its saving rate in order to ensure sustainable growth, capital formation, and the mobilization of domestic resources. Saving is essential for capital formation which enhances production, investment, and employment and these factors lead to the growth of an economy. Saving around the world vary widely according to the national income of a concerned nation. A higher saving rate tends to go hand in hand with a higher income growth rate as there is the existence of a virtuous cycle of savings and prosperity.

Nepal's Gross Domestic Saving (GDS) was estimated to be around 18.1% of GDP in the fiscal year 2019/20, and Gross National Savings (GNS) to be 46% in that fiscal year. There is a potential role of remittance in the

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capital formation of Nepal. However, Nepal is facing a problem of proper channeling of these funds into the productive sector. Most of the valued foreign currency is used for consumption purposes in Nepal, as there is a lack of proper mechanisms to channel the national savings into domestic investment (Acharya, 2021).

There are many barriers to the financial development of Nepal. The civil war of Nepal from 1996 to 2006 and the political turmoil until 2018 are also considered to be the major barriers to Nepal's lower financial development (Bist & Bista, 2018). The Nepalese economy witnessed a lower saving rate. Due to its poor saving rate, Nepal lags behind in both modern technology and developmental endeavors. By 2030, Nepal's government hopes to move it from the low-income group of the World Bank to the middle-income group (World Bank, 2021). Saving also plays an important role in the growth of an economy as it supports capital formation and boosts investment if saving is utilized in a productive sector. As savings are required for the overall development of a nation, it is important to know the factors that affect the gross domestic saving of a nation.

In this study, two variables, interest rate, and inflation rate are considered as the determinants of National Savings of Nepal. Gross Domestic Savings is taken as the proxy variable of National Savings. The purpose of this study is to find the effect of interest rate and inflation on the national saving of Nepal and examining the trend of Lending Interest Rate, Consumer Price Index, Per Capita Income, GDP, and Gross Domestic Savings. Further analysis is conducted to find the relationship of the Lending Interest Rate, Consumer Price Index, Per Capita Income, and GDP with the Gross Domestic Savings of Nepal.

Therefore, this study analyzed the two important macroeconomic factors: inflation and interest rate, and their effect on the Gross Domestic Savings of Nepal. Nepal is still facing the problem of a low saving rate. There are various factors that determine the saving rate of a nation. Inflation and interest rate has been taken as factors that affect the GDS of Nepal, as these two macroeconomic variables are the major determinant of the saving rate of any nation.

Literature Review

Life Cycle Hypothesis

The life cycle hypothesis states that individual consumption in any time periods depends on i) resources available to the individual ii) the rate of return on his capital and iii) the age of the individual. According to the life cycle hypothesis, a rational consumer plans consumption on the basis of all his resources and allocates his income to consumption over time so that maximizes his total utility over his lifetime (Dwivedi, 2015). Most of the people earn regular income and save for their retirement can be taken as an example of this theory. The basic proposition of the life cycle theory of consumption is that a representative individual maximizes her utility from life-time consumption, and savings are residuals reflecting differences between individual income and consumption

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Interest Rate on savings

Interest rate is one of the variables that can affect the decision to save. The Life Cycle Theory introduced that the net effect of the interest rate on saving is unclear. The interest rate can affect savings in two ways Substitution effect and Income effect. The substitution effect implies that a higher interest rate increases the current price of consumption relative to the future price, and thus it affects savings positively. According to income effect an increase in the interest rate increases the life time income and so increase consumption and reduce savings. The interest rate will have positive impact on savings ratio only when the substitution effect dominates the income effect (Modigliani & Brumberg, 1954). In developing countries like Nepal, the financial markets are still not well developed, substitution effect is expected to be much greater than income effect, and thus real interest rate is likely to have a positive impact on domestic savings.

Inflation a growing concern

Inflation rate has been taken as one of the issues which affect the saving rate of a nation. Generally, we understand inflation as the rise in general price level. Inflation might influence saving through its impact on real wealth. The value of wealth decreases with the higher value of inflation and through the wealth effect it negatively affects consumption and thus enhancing saving. The saving ratio is positively related to the rate of domestic inflation as long as inflation is mild, but if inflation rate is excessive, it starts affecting the saving negatively (Thirlwall,1974).

In life cycle model the impact of inflation on saving is through its role in determining real interest rate. This is based on the assumption of the absence of money illusion in saving behavior and absence of the real balance effect of inflation. Due to inflation, there is uncertainty in future income streams and thus it can lead to higher saving on precautionary ground. This case is highly true in case of developing countries like Nepal as their income prospects are uncertain and on the other side inflation could impact the saving through its impact on real wealth.

Abou El-Seoud (2014) conducted the study on the Effect of Interest rate, Inflation rate and GDP on National Savings Rate with an objective to investigate the effect of Real GDP, interest rate and inflation rate on national savings in Bahrain by adopting Augmented Dickey Fuller unit root test and cointegration test to examine the long run relationship between the variables under study. The findings of the study show that real GDP growth rate has positive impact on national savings in short run and it is significant at 5% level in the long run. Likewise, nominal interest rate has positive and significant effect on national savings at 1% significant level in short run but in long run it appears to be positive but insignificant and inflation rate has positive and significant effect on both short run and long run in the economy of Bahrain.

Aleemi,Ahmed & Tariq (2015) studied on the determinants of saving in Pakistan with an objective to analyze the impact and relationship between national saving rate and some selected determinants of saving namely inflation, real interest rate, real GDP growth rate and Government current expenditure, by using annual data for the period of 1980 to 2010. In order to find out the result a dynamic regression model with the autoregressive-moving average (ARMA) specification model was used and this study found out that

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inflation, interest rate and government expenditures negatively affects the saving rate during the study period.

Khan, Teng, Neuman & Jadoon, (2017) analyzed Determinants of National Savings from South Asian Countries with an objective to find the determinant of national saving of six south Asian countries Nepal, Srilanka, Pakistan, Bangladesh, India and Bhutan by using the panel data from 1989-2013, by applying econometrics techniques such as correlation matrix, descriptive statistics and fixed effect model. The findings of this research paper from the use of fixed effect model indicate that inflation, tax and gross domestic product have statistically significant effect on the gross domestic savings while the research paper also shows that per capita income, interest, money supply growth and age dependency ratio have non-significant effect on gross domestic saving. Likewise, other variables such as inflation, tax revenue and gross domestic product showed positive effect on gross domestic saving.

Hallaq (2003) studied Determinants of Private Savings of Jordan using the Ordinary Least Square method and instrumental variable methods. The data has been accumulated from the period of 1976-2000 for the study. The dependency ratio, Government savings, GDP growth rate, consumer credit market, public expenditure, real interest rate, and inflation rate are taken as the determinants of private savings. The findings of the study show that the dependency ratio is found to have negative and significant relation with private savings. 1% increase in Government savings shows a decline in private savings by 0.36%. The author has found that there is a statistically significant positive relationship between the GDP growth rate and the private savings of Jordan. The expansion of the consumer credit industry also appears to have a favorable effect on individual savings. According to this study the private savings in Jordan is also affected by real interest rates, inflation rates, and terms of trade.

Cheng & Li (2014) conducted research on Cross country's Effects of Inflation on National Savings with the objective of finding out the effects of inflation rates on national savings. The authors have used both simple regression and multiple regression models by taking into account the unemployment rate, HDI, population, and income per capita. Cross-sectional data sets of more than a hundred countries are used and STATA has been used to interpret the data sets and find how significant the effect is. The authors found that inflation has statistically significant positive effects on national savings in both simple and multiple regression models.

Corsepius & Fischer (1986) conducted a study on Interest rate policies and domestic savings mobilization: A survey of the empirical evidence of Asian countries with an objective to present a more comprehensive survey of empirical studies on the interest elasticity of saving in order to determine whether high positive interest elasticities are reasonable assumption for developing countries. In this study empirical work has been done for Asian economies by using regression analysis of saving function of 13 Asian countries with respect to the estimated coefficient of the interest variables by different aggregates and types of saving covering the periods of 1950-1983. From this study authors found out that the interest elasticity of savings in Asian countries shows that financial savings react positively on a rise in real rates of interest. A positive interest elasticity of financial saving is however not enough to conclude that funds for investment purposes can be increased by higher interest rate.

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Basically, Nepalese economy is a consumption-oriented economy. Fifth Household survey report by NRB shows that Nepalese people spend about 85% of their income on consumption (NRB, 2015). This shows that saving rate of Nepal is very low. Nepal is experiencing slow economic growth rate and one reason may be the lower saving rate in the Nepalese economy. The Gross Domestic Savings of Nepal since 1975-2016 were around 11% of the GDP (World Bank, 2018). As saving is the preliminary element for investment and investment is important for the economic growth and development as it leads to income generation.

In the case of Nepal, in order to graduate from low-income countries to middle income countries the priority must be given to saving aspect of the nation as it helps in boosting investment and income generation. So, it is important to know the factors behind the low saving rate of Nepal and what are the determinants of saving rate in an economy. Many researchers have shown that interest rate, inflation, GDP growth rate as the determinants of national savings. As there is lack of such studies in case of Nepal, this study has been conducted in order to know the impact of inflation and interest rate on national savings of Nepal.

Methodology of the Study

This research is quantitatively designed. This study has adopted deductive method for the analysis of variables. It is based on descriptive research design as descriptive research design is used for the understanding of the subjects or topics in details. The variables of this study are interest rate, inflation, GDP, Per capita income are regressors whereas GDS is regressand.

This study was conducted to find out the impact of interest rate and inflation on Gross Domestic Savings of Nepal. Data for conducting this research has been collected from secondary sources. Data are accumulated from the various sources like official website of Nepal Rastra Bank, Ministry of Finance, National Planning Commission, and Central Bureau of Statistics, World Bank and so on. This study analyzed the data by using averages and by testing causal relationship of the variables.

Model Specification

In this section the researcher has specified the empirical model of the study as follows:

$$\text{Log GDS} = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{LogCPI} + \beta_2 \text{LogLIR} + \beta_3 \text{LogGDP} + \beta_4 \text{LogPCI} + \varepsilon$$

GDS = Gross Domestic Savings

LIR = Lending Interest rate

CPI = Consumer Price Index

GDP = Gross Domestic Product

PCI = Per Capita Income

β_s = slope of given variable

ε = error term

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Data Analysis and Estimation Techniques

In this study we used simple descriptive statistics and inferential tool (multiple regression model with logarithm transformation) for estimating the relationship between dependent and independent variables. This study used Microsoft Excel for trend analysis and E-views software for estimating the relationship between dependent and independent variables.

Data analysis and interpretation

The results on the trend analysis shows the change in components of GDS, LRI, CPI, GDP and PCI between the year 2000 to 2020 of 20 years. The trend analysis is represented in different figures generated from an analyzing software Microsoft Excel. All the five components for economy representation are between 2000 to 2020 which represent the trend of growth and decrease. Although Nepal's economy is not as strong as the developed country's economy, it is evident from the analysis that growth can be achieved from the efficient running of the economy cycle.

Table 1 PCI, LIR, CPI, GDP AND GDS FROM YEAR 2000/01 TO 2019/20

Year	Per capita income	Lending interest rate	Consumer price index	GDP at producers price (in million)	Gross domestic savings (in million)
2000/01	19072	11	37.2	441,518.00	51,501.50
2001/02	19410	10.75	38.3	459,442.60	43,599.40
2002/03	20337	11.25	40.1	492,230.80	42,140.60
2003/04	21689	11	41.7	536,749.10	63,063.80
2004/05	23292	10.88	43.6	589,411.70	68,110.40
2005/06	25279	10.75	47.1	654,084.10	58,756.90
2006/07	28905	10.75	49.8	727,827.00	71,452.50
2007/08	31946	10	53.2	815,658.20	80,188.30
2008/09	38172	10.75	59.9	988,272.00	93,230.00
2009/10	45435	11	65.6	1,192,774.00	136,589.00
2010/11	51594	11.70	71.9	1,366,953.00	190,923.00
2011/12	56880	12.40	77.8	1,527,344.00	167,805.00
2012/13	62283	12.09	85.5	1,695,011.00	178,882.20
2013/14	71225	10.55	93.3	1,964,540.00	234,227.40
2014/15	76201	9.62	100	2,120,470.00	196,103.00
2015/16	79528	8.86	109.9	2,248,691.00	91,644.00
2016/17	92031	11.33	114.8	2,674,493.00	359,206.00
2017/18	103335	12.47	119.7	3,044,927.00	506,418.00
2018/19	117268	12.13	125.1	3,458,793.00	656,235.00
2019/20	126018	10.11	132.84	3,767,043.00	681,971.00

Source: Nepal Rastra Bank Current Macro Economic and Financial Situation 2019/20

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Trend of Gross Domestic Savings

This section has intended to provide information about the trend of GDS of Nepal from 2000/01 to 2019/20. Gross Domestic Savings in the fiscal year 2000/01 is 51,501.50 million rupees which have become 6,81,971.00 million rupees in 2019/20. The average GDS during the study year shows 1,98,602.35 million rupees. GDS is below average from the year 2000/01 to 2009/10 whereas in the year 2010/11 GDS is above average that is 190,923 million rupees and again in the year 2011/12 GDS is below average. Likewise, GDS from 2012/13 to 2014/15 GDS is above average. GDS decreased in the year 2015/16 which is 91,644 million rupees which is due to a massive earthquake and economic blockade by India. From the year 2016/17 to 2019/20 the GDS of Nepal is above average. The trend of GDS seems to fluctuate during these study periods.

Figure 1 Percentage Change in Gross Domestic Savings

Figure 1 shows the percentage change in GDS from fiscal year 2000/01 to 2019/20. The trend shows huge fluctuation in change in GDS from beginning of the study year till the end. The trend line shows ups and down in GDS. The ups and down trend are smaller in the year 2000/01 to 2013/14. The fluctuation is higher from the year 2014/15 to 2019/20. There is rapid downfall of GDS in the year 2015/16 due to devastating earthquake and economic blockade from India. In year 2016/17 the economic resilience leads to the increment in overall economic activities and it results in improvement of GDS. The figure shows huge increment in savings in year 2016/17 and we can see percentage change in GDS has decreased highly in year 2017/18 and again we see downward trend in GDS from FY 2017/18 to FY 2019/20.

Trend of Lending Interest Rate

Lending Interest is one of the independent variables used in this study. LIR is the interest rate charged by the bank for a loan to the customer. The figure 2 depicted the lending interest rate from FY 200/01 to 2019/20.

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The average lending interest rate is 10.97%. The LIR seems to be around average among all the FY taken in this study.

Figure 2 Percentage Change in Lending Interest Rate

Figure 2 depicted the trend of lending interest rate of Nepal from FY 2000/01 to 2019/20. The figure shows that there is fluctuation in interest rate. The trend line of LIR is ups and down from the beginning till the end of the study period. We can see ups and down of LIR is smaller from FY 2000/01 to 2011/12 and there is increment in fluctuation from year 2012/13 to 2019/20. The percentage change in lending interest rate is higher from FY 2015/16 to 2019/20. The interest rate has been increased by 27.878% in FY 2016/17 as compared to the previous FY 2015/16. We can see the downturn of LIR after it reaches highest in FY 2016/17.

Figure 1 shows that there is huge increment of GDS in the year 2016/17 and in the same year there is huge increment of percentage change in LIR. From this trend analysis we can say that increase in interest rate leads to an increase in Gross Domestic Savings. Therefore, from figure 1 and 2 it can be analyzed that there is positive effect of Lending Interest Rate on Gross Domestic Savings of Nepal.

Trend of Inflation

Figure 3 shows the trend of consumer price index from the year 2000/01 to 2019/20. The CPI is 37.2 in the fiscal year 2000/01 and it has reached 132.84 in the fiscal year 2019/20. CPI is 75.367 on average. CPI is below average in 11 years from FY 2000/01 to 2011/12. CPI is above average from the fiscal year 2012/13 to 2019/20. CPI has been increasing from the beginning of the study period till the end of the study period that is from FY 2000/01 to 2019/10. The trend of percentage change in CPI is explained by the figure 3.

Figure 3 Percentage Change in Consumer Price Index

Figure 3 depicted the trend of percentage change in CPI. The figure shows trend of percentage change in CPI seems like wave. The figure shows that change in CPI is ups and down. The fluctuation is between the range it is neither too high nor too low.

Trend of Gross Domestic Product (GDP)

Figure 4 shows the trend of Gross Domestic Product from FY 2000/01 to 2019/20. The GDP is 441,518.00 million rupees in the year 2000/01 which has reached 37,67,043.00 million rupees in the year 2019/20. GDP is 1,538,311.63 million rupees on average. The trend of percentage change in GDP is explained by the figure 4.

Figure 4 Percentage Change in Gross Domestic Product

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In figure 4 percentage change in GDP from FY 2000/01 to 2019/20 has been depicted. We can see in the figure from year 2000/01 to 2008/09 the trend line shows the increasing trend of GDP. In FY 2008/09 we see trend line at its highest point that means percentage change in GDP is higher at that period as compared to previous years. After 2008/09 there starts a decreasing trend of GDP till year 2012/13 and again there is increment in GDP in the year 2013/14. In year 2015/16 the percentage change in GDP has fallen to 6.046%. After year 2015/16 again there is increment in GDP in year 2016/17. After year 2017/18 we can see ups and down in GDP but the fluctuation is not large as compared to year 2015/16.

Trend of Per Capita Income (PCI)

The per capita income in the year 2000/01 is 19072 rupees which have become 126018 rupees in the fiscal year 2019/20. Table 4.4 shows that the average per capita income is 55495 rupees. Per capita income is below average from the year 2000/01 to 2010/11. From the year 2011/12 to 2019/20 PCI is above average. Per Capita Income has been increasing from the beginning that is year 2000/01 to 2019/20 but there is fluctuation in percentage change in PCI. The percentage change in PCI is shown in the figure below as figure 5.

Figure 5 Percentage Change in Per Capita Income

In the figure 5 Percentage change in per capita income is depicted. The trend line shows increasing trend from year 2000/01 to 2006/07. The trend of PCI is ups and down from year 2006/07 to 2019/20. The trend is fluctuated from the beginning of the observation period till the end of observation.

Relationship between dependent and independent variables

In this part log regression model had been used in order to investigate the relationship of interest rate and inflation with Gross Domestic Savings of Nepal.

Table 2 relations interest rate, inflation with GDP savings

$$\text{Log GDS} = -37.03 - 6.92\text{CPI} + 1.01\text{LIR} - 0.12\text{PCI} + 5.49\text{GDP}$$

Std. Error	(7.99)	(1.63)	(0.57)	(2.62)	(2.52)
T statistics	(-4.63)	(-4.23)	(1.75)	(-0.047)	(2.18)
Probability	(.0003)	(.0007)	(.0100)	(.0963)	(.0455)
R-squared = 0.968					Durbin Watson stat = 1.57
F stat = 114.20					Prob (F stats) = 0.0000

Table 3 Dependent Variable: LOG (GDS in MILLION)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-37.03231	7.992342	-4.633474	0.0003
LOG(CPI)	-6.920986	1.634016	-4.235568	0.0007
LOG(LIR)	1.006435	0.574263	1.752569	0.1001
LOG(PCI)	-0.123807	2.624189	-0.047179	0.9630
LOG(GDP__IN_MILLION_)	5.498616	2.520542	2.181522	0.0455
R-squared	0.968207	Mean dependent variables		11.80470
Adjusted R-squared	0.959729	S.D. dependent variables		0.882044
S.E. of regression	0.177006	Akaike info criterion		-0.412954
Sum squared resid	0.469964	Schwarz criterion		-0.164020
Log likelihood	9.129535	Hannan-Quinn criteria.		-0.364359
F-statistic	114.2007	Durbin-Watson stat		1.574741
Prob (F-statistic)	0.000000			

Method: Least Squares,
 Date: 05/07/23 Time: 21:04
 Sample: 1 20
 Included observations: 20

The coefficient of CPI is -6.92 which means, 1% change in CPI results in 6.92% negative change in Gross Domestic Savings of Nepal. The t statistics for CPI is - 4.23 and its absolute value is 4.23. Here, the P value

for CPI is 0.007 which is less than 0.05. Hence, it shows that there is a statistically significant relationship between Consumer Price Index and Gross Domestic Savings of Nepal.

In the case of LIR, the coefficient of LIR is 1.01 and it shows that 1% change in Lending Interest Rate results in 1.1 % positive change in GDS. The P value for LIR is 0.100(>0.05), here we accept null hypothesis which means there is no any significant relationship between Lending Interest Rate and GDS of Nepal.

Similarly, the coefficient for PCI is -0.12 which means 1% change in PCI results in 0.12% negative change in GDS of Nepal. The P value for PCI is greater than 0.05 (0.96), which means there is no any significant relationship between PCI and GDS.

Likewise, the coefficient for GDP is 5.49. It means 1% change in GDP result in 5.69% positive change in GDS of Nepal. The p value for GDP is 0.04 (<0.05) which means there is a significant relationship between GDP and GDS.

The DW stats from the analysis is found to be 1.57. As a rule of thumb DW test statistics value range of 1.5 to 2.5 are relatively normal and acceptable. Therefore, in this regression model there is no problem of autocorrelation.

Conclusion

This study investigated the effect of interest rate and inflation on national savings of Nepal simply by using multiple regression with log model using annual data covering from the period of 2000/01 to 2019/20. The result of the regression model shows that there is significant but negative relationship between inflation and Gross Domestic Savings of Nepal and positive but insignificant relationship between Lending interest rate and GDS of Nepal. Likewise, per capita income shows the insignificant relationship with GDS and Gross Domestic Product and GDS are positively related with each other.

References

- Abou El-Seoud, M. S. (2014). The Effect of Interest Rate, Inflation Rate and GDP on National Saving Rate. *Global Journal of Commerce and Management Perspective, 1-7*.
- Acharya, S. (2021, march). Nepal Economic Forum. Retrieved August 13, 2022 from <https://nepaleconomicforum.org/neftake/mobilization-of-domestic-savings-in-nepal/>
- Ahmad, M.& Asghar, T. (2010),” Estimation of Saving Behavior in Pakistan using microdata”. Allama Iqbal Open University. Islamabad
- Aleemi, A. R., Ahmed, S., & Tariq, M. (2015). The determinants of savings: Empirical evidence from Pakistan. *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research, 4(1)*.
- Bist, J. P., & Bista, N. B. (2018). Finance–growth nexus in Nepal: An application of the ARDL approach in the presence of structural breaks. *Vikalpa, 43 (4)*, 236-249.
- Cheng, Q., & Li, X. (2014). Cross--Country Effects of Inflation on National Savings.

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- Corsepius, U., & Fischer, B. (1986). Interest rate policies and domestic savings mobilization: A survey of the empirical evidence of Asian countries (No. 267). Kiel Working Paper.
- Dwivedi, D. N. (2015). *Macroeconomics: theory and policy*. Tata McGraw-Hill Education.
- Hallaq, S. (2003). Determinants of private savings: The case of Jordan (1976-2000). *Journal of King Saud University Administrative Sciences*, 15(2), 83-94.
- Khan, S. M. (1993). Domestic resource mobilisation: A structural approach. *The Pakistan Development Review* 32 (4), 1067-1078.
- Khan, M. I., Teng, J. Z., Khan, M. K., Nauman, M., & Jadoon, A. U (2017). Determinants of National Saving: Evidence from South Asian Countries. *European Academic Research*, 8, 4158-4189.
- Mboweni, T. T. (2008). Monetary policy, inflation targeting and inflation pressures. *The Bureau for Economic Research Annual Conference*. Johannesburg: South African Reserve Bank.
- Modigliani, F., & Brumberg, R. (1954). Utility analysis and the consumption function: An interpretation of cross-section data. *Journal of Economics*, 1(1), 388-436.
- Nga, M. T. (2007). *An investigative analysis into the saving behaviors of poor households in developing countries: With specific reference to South Africa* [Doctoral dissertation, University of the Western Cape].
- Rajbhandari, M.M.S. (2020). Economy Pandemic: A Crisis Management towards Post COVID- 19. A Commentary Opinion. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences* 4(1), 1-8.
- Rehman H.U, Faridi M.Z, Bashir F. (2010). Household Saving Behavior in Pakistan: A Case of Multan District. *Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences* 30(1) 17-29.
- Sen, A. (1999). Commodities and capabilities. *OUP Catalogue*.
- Startz, R. (2019). EViews Illustrated. *University of California: Santa Barbara, CA, USA*.
- Thirlwall, A. P. (1974). Inflation and the savings ratio across countries. *The Journal of Development Studies*, 10(2), 154-174.
- World Bank (2021). *Climbing higher: toward a middle-income Nepal*.
<https://www.worldbank.org/en/region/sar/publication/climbing-higher-toward-a-middle-income-country>.

